

The Host Galaxies of Hybrid Type Ia/IIn Supernovae

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ABSTRACT

Observations have yielded at least four unusual supernovae, which look spectroscopically very much like Type Ia SNe but have prominent narrow H α emission lines, and have thus been dubbed, Type IIa. The following four SNe have been studied extensively: SN 1997cy, SN 1999E, SN 2002ic, SN 2005gj. We seek to shed some light on the source of the explosion by closely examining the environments of these SNe. We measure the metallicity and star formation rates for three of the host galaxies (the galaxy spectrum for the SN 2005gj host galaxy was still contaminated with emission from the SN) and compared them to those of more well-studied SNe. The measurements show low metallicity and star formation rates, the former does not agree well with classification as a Type Ia. While these measurements do not strongly indicate a particular progenitor system, they may be able to form a profile of possible galactic characteristics to look for future objects of this type.

1. Introduction

Supernovae are classified according to their spectral features. Two prominent types are Type Ia and Type II. There are also Type Ib and Type Ic as well as a few more peculiar types (Filippenko 1997). Type Ia SNe are characterized by their strong Silicon lines and lack of Hydrogen. The most widely accepted theory for the progenitor of these explosions is a white dwarf that, through mass accretion, has reached the Chandrasehker mass limit and exploded. Type II SNe are characterized by the presence of hydrogen in their spectra, and are known to result from the core collapse of a massive star at the end of its lifetime. One particular subclassification is that of SN Type IIn, which has broad, weak absorption lines

and strong narrow Hydrogen emission lines (Filippenko 1997). The four we discuss here: SN 1997cy, SN 1999E, SN 2002ic, SN 2005gj, all have characteristics from both classifications.

SN 1997cy was one of the brightest SN discovered at it’s time, $M_R = -20.5$, $H_0 = 71$ at discovery (after maximum light). (Germany et al. 2000). For the rest of this paper we assume $H_0 = 71 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. Germany et al. (2000) also point out that SN 1997cy is a hybrid SN with late time Fe lines as is seen in Type Ias, and narrow $H\alpha$ as is seen in Type IIns, but suggest it is a core collapse SN. Rigon et al. (2003) report on SN 1999E, and point out the striking similarities between it and SN 1999cy including the prominent, narrow $H\alpha$ line and unusual brightness ($M_V = -19.7$) (after maximum light). Although both these papers suggest a relation between these explosions and gamma-ray bursts because of their high luminosities, this has yet to be confirmed.

Hamuy et al. (2003) originally classified SN 2002ic ($M_B \approx -20.3$, $M_V \approx -20.5$) as a Type Ia because of it’s strong Si and Fe lines and suggests that it underwent significant mass loss before it’s explosion such that the $H\alpha$ came from the circum-stellar medium (CSM). However, Deng et al. (2004) point out that the $H\alpha$ line is more characteristic of a Type IIn, and point out it’s similarities with SNe 1997cy and 1999E and proposes a new classification, Type IIa.

Aldering et al. (2006) ($m_v \approx 17.5$ We calculate an absolute magnitude, $M_V \approx -19.5$) in their observations of SN 2005gj captured the earliest spectra of any of these Type IIa Supernovae which showed almost no relation to a Type Ia, but had very prominent, narrow $H\alpha$ emission line. They do point out how similar SN 2005gj is to SN 2002ic, but disagree with the comparison of SN 2002ic with a Type Ia, pointing out the effects of radiative coupling with the CSM. They also report a starburst event beginning $200 \pm 70 \text{ Myr}$ ago.

There have been a few more observations of SNe that fit the Type IIa class that have been discovered recently, but the four we have discussed are the most well studied. It’s

clear from the various reports on these objects that they are unique and their exact nature is unknown.

SNe 1997cy, 1999E, 2002ic and 2005gj have all been thoroughly studied across multiple wavelengths including radio, infrared, optical and x-ray. What is lacking though is a thorough comparison of their host galaxies. It has been observed that core collapse SNe reside in young, spiral galaxies because they come from the explosions of massive stars with short lifetimes. Type Ias, on the other hands, come from older spiral and elliptical galaxies populated with ancient white dwarf stars.

We will use metallicity as an indicator of stellar age. Galactic metallicity is a measure of the ratio of oxygen to hydrogen in a galaxy. This ratio is a good indicator of the ratio of other less common elements to hydrogen as well. As a galaxy ages, it's metallicity increases as more and more heavier elements are fused in the cores of stars and in the explosions of supernovae although the precise relationship between age and metallicity and age is not well known and depends on many different parameters. A galaxy with a high metallicity is probably old and likely has a larger population of white dwarfs while a galaxy of low metallicity is probably very young, and likely has a larger population of high-mass stars and a lower concentration of white dwarfs because low mass stars are so long lived.

We will also use metallicity to examine how different these galaxies are from the galaxies of more normal SNe. Metallicity is good for comparison because it tells you something about the age of stars in the galaxy, which hints at the types of SNe that might be observed from that galaxy. We know that there exist correlations between galaxy metallicity and galaxy mass, and between galaxy metallicity and galaxy luminosity (Tremonti et al. 2004), which we can use to learn more about the Type IIa galaxies in comparison to other galaxies.

2. Observations

The galaxy spectra were all obtained with the Magellan telescope using the LDSS3 spectrograph. The exposure times are given in Table 1. All spectra were taken during December 2006. The spectra are shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8. Because we see no broad features in the spectra for the earlier three SNe host galaxies, we do not expect that they were contaminated by light from the SNe themselves. The host galaxy spectra of SN 2005gj were taken too soon after the SNe itself and there are clear broad features in the spectra indicating contamination. For this reason, we did not use these spectra and all reported metallicity values corresponding to this galaxy come from Aldering et al. (2006). All the data were reduced using standard packages in IRAF. The line fluxes were calculated using `splot` in IRAF by interactively fitting a Gaussian to the emission line. The spectra were also corrected for extinction using the IRAF package `deredden` with an extinction parameter $R = 3.1$. Where,

$$R = \frac{A(V)}{E(B - V)} \quad (1)$$

We assumed an intrinsic value of $H\alpha/H\beta = 3$ and tried different values of $E(B - V)$ until the spectra reproduced that ratio.

3. Methods

To calculate the metallicities we use the method presented in Kewley & Ellison (2008) which gives the metallicity, referred to as $12 + \log(O/H)$, as,

$$12 + \log(O/H) = 8.73 - 0.32 \times O3N2 \quad (2)$$

where O3N2 is given by,

$$O3N2 = \log \left[\left(\frac{[OIII] \lambda 5007}{H\beta} \right) / \left(\frac{[NII] \lambda 6584}{H\alpha} \right) \right]$$

The inputs to Eqn. 2 are the fluxes of the corresponding spectral lines we measure from our galaxy spectra. All the measurements for metallicity contain a systematic error of about 0.1 dex. We also calculate an estimate for star formation within the aperture galaxy. This is done using the luminosity of the H α line as given by Kennicutt (1998),

$$\text{SFR} (M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = 7.9 \times 10^{42} L(\text{H}\alpha) (\text{erg s}^{-1}) \quad (3)$$

To convert from our measured flux, we simply apply the inverse square law using a luminosity distance calculated using a calculator by Wright (2006).

$$L = 4\pi d_L^2 F \quad (4)$$

Since, it is too difficult to extrapolate our SFR to the rest of the galaxy or find an adequate way to compare to other galaxy types, no statistics were performed using SFR. They can still be used to give a qualitative picture of the galaxies, however. The final values for metallicities and SFR are given in Table 3

Our spectra for the host galaxy of SN 2005gj are still contaminated with light from the SN itself so we quote the value of metallicity in Aldering et al. (2006), which gives $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.25 \pm 0.05$.

We also report on photometry of the galaxies from the USNO-B1 catalogue. DSS images of the galaxies are shown in Figs. 9, 10, 11, and 12. We have converted the apparent magnitudes, given by m into absolute magnitudes, given by M using

$$M = m - 5 \log(d_L) - 5 \quad (5)$$

which we compare to the Luminosity-Metallicity relation calculated in Tremonti et al. (2004), which also presents a Mass-Metallicity relation. A qualitative contour was created from Fig. 4 from Tremonti et al. (2004) using Dexter. The contour is an attempt to show the general location of the vast majority of the SDSS galaxies on that plot. We use this to get a qualitative idea of how regular or irregular these galaxies are.

Seeing as these SN have been labeled as a cross between Type Ia and Type II_n, we compare their host galaxy metallicities to those of the host galaxies of both Type Ia and Type II_n SNe to look for a correlation with either group. We also compare the metallicities to those of Type I_bs and I_cs as well, to ensure we do not prematurely rule out any other possibilities. We obtain a sample of metallicities of core-collapse SNe host galaxies from Kelly & Kirshner (2011) and a sample of Type Ia host galaxy metallicities from D’Andrea et al. (2011). For the Type Ia SNe we select those galaxies that are not associated with an active galactic nucleus. We compare the metallicities both qualitatively and quantitatively, plotting the metallicities of the Type II_as on histograms of the metallicities of the other four types. We also perform a Kolomogorov-Smirnov test to see if the Type II_a group is statistically different from any of the other four types. The results of the KS test are given in Table 5

One important factor that may affect our interpretation of these objects comes from selection biases. D’Andrea et al. (2011) uses galaxies from SDSS II in a way that gives a representative sample of Type Ia host galaxies. Kelly & Kirshner (2011) however use mainly targetted galaxies so they are probably brighter and more metal-rich than a true representative sample.

Another very important issue that can potentially affect our results is the method used to calibrate metalicity to emmision lines. We made sure to select only the galaxies measured using the PP04 method from Kelly & Kirshner (2011) but the D’Andrea et al. (2011) sample reported using a different method, KD02.

4. Discussion

We can see from Table 4 that these are dim galaxies with low metallicities, except for SN 1999E. A quick look at Fig. 14 shows how these galaxies differ from the best fit obtained from the SDSS data. They are all clearly outside the contour. Taking metallicity to be an indicator of stellar age, we could expect that these galaxies have a younger population of stars that haven't had time to undergo metal-enriching processes. We would then suspect that, for a galaxy like this we would not see a very large population of white dwarf stars which points to the possibility that these Type IIa objects result from core-collapse. If however, these objects were related to Type Ias, then they would have to have rather short delay times in order to accrete enough mass to reach the Chandrasekhar mass limit and we would also expect to eventually find them in elliptical galaxies, which is something we haven't observed yet.

Our first indication of the nature of these objects comes from Fig. 13, where we can visually rule out the Type Ib and Ic classifications which is what we expected since these objects showed no indication of being either type. Since the Type II_n distribution extends to lower metallicities more so than the Type Ia distribution, we can qualitatively say that these objects have a better chance of being from a Type II_n-like galaxy.

Our quantitative indication of these object types comes from the results of the Kolomogorov-Smirnovi (KS) test. This test measures the probability that two distributions come from the same parent distribution. A p value of < 0.05 indicates that the two groups are statistically different and do not originate from the same parent distribution. We can see from Table 5 that the Type IIa group is statistically different from the Type Ib, Ic, and more informatively, the Type Ia. This indicates that there is actually something different between the Type IIa host galaxies and those for Type II_n. The KS test requires a minimum group size of four, which is the exact amount that we have.

5. Conclusions

Our observations of the host galaxies of Type IIa SNe points to the conclusion that these came from Type II_n like galaxies. While this does not tell us what they are, it gives us an indication of where to look. These objects are incredibly bright and their lightcurves fade slowly. So, seeing as so few of them have been observed, this means that they are incredibly rare. To better understand these objects, we would want to find more of them, and to do this, our data suggests to look at less luminous, lower metallicity galaxies.

Future work would include calibrating the metallicities used in the D’Andrea et al. (2011) sample so that they can be compared to our sample, or recalculate our sample using the KD04 method. We would also attempt to collect more core collapse host galaxy metallicities from untargeted surveys, so as to eliminate our selection bias. A full analysis of these host galaxies would include a more thorough analysis of galaxy mass and metallicity. To get better photometric results we would use the acquisition images acquired during the process of obtaining spectra.

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7. Tables and Figures

SN	Red	Blue
1997cy	750	1200
1999E	500	900
2002ic	900	900
2005gj	900	900

Table 1: Exposure times in seconds for the host galaxy for the red ($\lambda = [3500, 5500]$) and blue $\lambda = [6000, 8000]$) spectra.

Line	SN 1997cy		SN 1999E		SN 2002ic	
	λ	Flux	λ	Flux	λ	Flux
OII λ 3727	3964	1.57×10^{-15}	3823	2.33×10^{-14}	3982	1.27×10^{-15}
H β	5170	2.77×10^{-16}	4986	3.32×10^{-15}	5279	4.17×10^{-16}
OIII λ 4959	5274	2.29×10^{-16}	5086	5.16×10^{-16}	5366	4.68×10^{-16}
OIII λ 5007	5325	5.15×10^{-16}	5135	1.65×10^{-15}	5402	1.20×10^{-15}
H α	6980	8.66×10^{-16}	6730	1.05×10^{-14}	7004	1.30×10^{-15}
NII6583	7002	4.89×10^{-17}	6751	4.68×10^{-15}	7026	2.83×10^{-17}

Table 2: Fluxes for the various emission lines of the host galaxies given in units of $\frac{\text{erg}}{\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^2}$ as well as the observed wavelengths that each line was measured at in angstroms.

Type	$12 + \log(O/H)$	Type	$12 + \log(O/H)$	Type	$12 + \log(O/H)$
Ia	8.71	Ia	8.79	Ib	8.72
Ia	8.6	Ia	9.05	Ib	8.74
Ia	8.92	Ia	9.08	Ib	8.74
Ia	8.85	Ia	8.53	Ic	8.53
Ia	8.91	Ia	8.96	Ic	8.71
Ia	8.62	Ia	8.94	Ic	8.76
Ia	8.92	Ia	9.07	Ic	8.86
Ia	9.03	IIIn	8.79	Ic	8.84
Ia	8.83	IIIn	8.36	Ic	8.74
Ia	9.00	IIIn	8.82	Ic	8.79
Ia	8.25	IIIn	8.84	Ic	8.83
Ia	8.37	IIIn	8.78	Ic	8.76
Ia	8.82	IIIn	8.75	Ic	8.76
Ia	8.72	IIIn	8.59	Ic	8.41
Ia	8.76	IIIn	8.83	Ic	8.84
Ia	8.81	IIIn	8.55	Ic	8.74
Ia	8.79	IIIn	8.4	Ic	8.88
Ia	8.85	IIIn	8.72	Ic	8.74
Ia	8.85	IIIn	8.83	Ic	8.56
Ia	9.06	IIIn	8.15	Ic	8.56
Ia	9.03	Ib	8.39	Ic	8.91
Ia	8.64	Ib	8.72	Ic	8.76
Ia	8.86	Ib	8.62	Ic	8.84
Ia	8.44	Ib	8.75	Ic	8.8
Ia	8.89	Ib	8.74	Ic	8.77
Ia	8.95	Ib	8.74	Ic	8.74
Ia	8.61	Ib	8.72	Ic	8.74
Ia	8.96	Ib	8.83	Ic	8.61
Ia	9.01	Ib	8.83	Ic	8.82
Ia	8.26	Ib	8.53	Ic	8.89
-	-	-	-	Ic	8.79

Table 3: Metallicities of Host Galaxies of SN from Kelly & Kirshner (2011) and D’Andrea et al. (2011)

SN	$12 + \text{Log}(O/H)$	SFR($M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)	Redshift	M_R	M_B
1997cy	8.24	0.06	0.063	-18.4	-17.7
1999E	8.72	0.11	0.025	-23.3	-22.7
2002ic	8.05	0.10	0.067	-19.7	-19.4
2005gj	8.25	-	0.062	-16.5	-16.0

Table 4: Properties of Host Galaxies of Type IIa SN including metallicity, star formation rate, redshift, and R and B absolute magnitudes.

Type	p
Ia	0.022
IIa	0.068
Ib	0.030
Ic	0.018

Table 5: Kolomogorov-Smirnov results. A p value of < 0.05 indicates that the Type IIa group is statically different than the reported group

Fig. 1.— A blue optical spectrum of the Host Galaxy of SN 1997cy

Fig. 2.— A red optical spectrum of the Host Galaxy of SN 1997cy

Fig. 3.— A blue optical spectrum of the Host Galaxy of SN 1999E

Fig. 4.— A red optical spectrum of the Host Galaxy of SN 1999E

Fig. 5.— A blue optical spectrum of the Host Galaxy of SN 2002ic

Fig. 6.— A red optical spectrum of the Host Galaxy of SN 2002ic

Fig. 7.— A blue optical spectrum of SN 2005gj that is not flux calibrated.

Fig. 8.— A red optical spectrum of SN 2005gj that is not flux calibrated.

Fig. 9.— SAO-DSS image of the host galaxy of SN 1997cy.

Fig. 10.— SAO-DSS image of the host galaxy of SN 1999E.

Fig. 11.— SAO-DSS image of the host galaxy of SN 2002ic.

Fig. 12.— SDSS image of the host galaxy of SN 2005gj.

Fig. 13.— Histograms of the metallicities of host galaxies of SNe from the two samples. Histograms are normalized to one at their peak. Arrows indicating the locations of the four Type IIa SNe.

Fig. 14.— A plot of the best fit line for the luminosity-metallicity relation for SDSS from Tremonti et al. (2004). Included are the positions of the Type IIa SNe as well as a rough contour showing the general location of the vast majority of SDSS galaxies.

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